

Title: Collaborative robotics for a natural and effective physical human-robot interaction

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Reasons that make the organizers' proposal relevant and interesting to the attendees of the IRIM3D 2024

The workshop aims to delve into the topic of collaborative robotics, with specific emphasis on natural and effective physical human-robot interaction. Such a topic, in fact, is extremely important in numerous contexts, such as industrial, assistive, and rehabilitation settings. Applications span co-transportation, co-assembly, collaborative mobile platforms, exoskeletons, etc. In these scenarios, the control of the human-robot interaction is important from many points of view. Safety is one of the highest priority KPIs: the human is in contact with the robot, and in some cases (e.g., exoskeletons) constrained to it. A natural interaction is also important to be established, to implement effective collaboration. Customized and adaptive controllers have also to be designed, so that a tailored robot behavior can be applied for each specific user.

In this context, the following topics will be addressed in the workshop:

- Human state monitoring
- Adaptive control strategies
- Machine learning for collaborative control
- Active preference learning for tailored interaction control tuning
- Exoskeleton control design and optimization

Speakers:

- Loris Roveda, Politecnico di Milano, IDSIA USI-SUPSI: occupational back-support exoskeleton: the EIT-M SUPERHUMAN project
- Arash Ajoudani, IIT: Task-Adaptive and Human-State Responsive Cobots for Industry and Healthcare
- Giorgio Nicola, STIIMA-CNR: Collaborative transport of deformable objects: from deformation estimation to role arbitration
- Stefani Mutti, SUPSI ITePS: Multi-Robot Path Planning and Control for Constrained Navigation

Schedule:

- Welcome (5 mins)
- Presentation: Arash Ajoudani (15 mins + 5 mins Q/A)
- Presentation: Giorgio Nicola (15 mins + 5 mins Q/A)
- Presentation: Stefano Mutti (15 mins + 5 mins Q/A)
- Presentation: Loris Roveda (15 mins + 5 mins Q/A)
- Conclusions (5 mins)